

ECONOMICS

TAX OBLIGATION OPTIMIZATION IN THE MINING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The article examines legal mechanisms and strategies for optimizing tax obligations for companies in the mining industry (MI). The primary types of taxes applicable to mining enterprises are explored. Special attention is given to legal tools for reducing tax burdens, such as tax incentives, international double taxation agreements, and depreciation policies. The use of strategies including transfer pricing, activity diversification, and multi-tier corporate structures for tax optimization in both international and national jurisdictions is analyzed. Examples of successful implementation of these strategies by major mining companies underscore their effectiveness in the context of globalization and increasing environmental requirements.

Keywords: Tax optimization, mining industry (MI), legal mechanisms, tax incentives, transfer pricing.

Introduction

The mining sector is crucial to the world economy, as it provides necessary materials to industrial and energy industries. Taxation is intricate and layered in multiple levels in this field. With strict regulations and increasing transparency demands, tax planning and optimization are crucial for mining companies due to these features.

In the era of globalization and increased competition, businesses strive to enhance productivity while also minimizing tax liabilities within legal boundaries. Tax optimization is currently the main method of increasing the financial efficiency and competitiveness of

a business. Nevertheless, a comprehensive comprehension of legal mechanisms and an examination of possible risks are essential for these procedures. The aim of this study is to systematize and analyze the legal mechanisms and tax optimization strategies applicable to companies in the mining sector.

Main part. Taxation features in the mining industry (MI)

The mining sector is a significant part of the USA economy. In 2023, the gross output of the industry reached \$701,7 billion (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Gross output of the mining sector in the USA in 2023, billion dollars [1]

Taxation in the MI is complex and subject to significant requirements from both national and international authorities. The specific nature of taxation for companies operating in this sector is determined by the scale of their activities, their substantial impact on natural resources, and the legislation of the countries where extraction takes place. As part of tax burden optimization, mining companies must consider a variety

of factors, including the diversity of applicable taxes and compliance with legal requirements.

Due to its specific characteristics, the MI is subject to multi-layered and specialized taxation, reflecting the importance of natural resources and the need to regulate environmental impact. Table 1 presents the primary types of taxes characteristic of mining companies.

Table 1.

Main types of taxes applicable to the MI [2, 3]

Type of tax	Description	Application features
Income tax	Tax on the net profit of companies after deduction of operating expenses.	The federal rate is 21%, and state corporate taxes may additionally apply (for example, in Nevada on profits from mining).
Sales and use tax	The tax applied to the purchase of equipment and materials used in mining.	It is set at the state and local government levels. There is no VAT as such.
Mineral extraction tax (severance tax)	A tax levied for the extraction of natural resources.	The rates and calculation methods depend on the state and the type of resource.
Environmental charges	Expenses related to compliance with environmental standards and compensation for environmental damage.	There are no specific environmental taxes, such as the carbon tax, at the federal level.
Customs duties	Taxes on the import of equipment and export of products.	Imported equipment may be subject to duties, export duties are usually absent.
Licensing fees and royalties	Payments for the right to extract minerals.	Mandatory royalties have been established for federal lands, the amount of which depends on the type of resource. On private lands, the conditions are stipulated in contracts.
Local taxes and fees	Taxes levied by local governments for infrastructure and community development.	These include property taxes, lease payments for land use and fees for infrastructure development.

According to the author, the tax system for mining companies is a complicated system that includes many taxes and fees with the goals of generating revenue and promoting sustainable natural resource management. This tax system considers the MI's substantial environmental effects, its capital-intensive structure, and the necessity of government assistance in areas where extraction occurs.

Legal mechanisms for tax optimization in the MI

One of the central tools for supporting the MI, stimulating investment activity, and attracting capital to strategically important projects is **government-provided tax incentives and preferences**. These include reduced rates on specific taxes, tax exemptions for certain periods, and special tax deductions. These measures reduce the financial burden on companies, creating opportunities for expanding extraction, modernizing equipment, and implementing innovative technologies. Companies can access numerous tax incentives and deductions that partially offset capital expenses during the development of deposits. For example, under the Internal Revenue Code (IRC), companies can deduct exploration and development costs, including drilling and geological exploration expenses. These deductions can be applied immediately or gradually, depending on the nature and duration of the projects.

Mining companies that work in various countries may encounter the issue of being taxed twice, where their profits are taxed in both the country where the resources are extracted and their home country. To deal with this problem, numerous nations, such as the USA, establish **bilateral double taxation treaties** to avoid companies being taxed twice on the same income [4]. These agreements control how taxing responsibilities are divided among countries, lowering risks for businesses and making investments more appealing. One

way a company can lower its tax liabilities in its home country is by using tax credits for taxes already paid in the country where resources were extracted. Tax exemptions could also be applied to certain categories of earnings, like dividends or interest. This enables companies to reduce their tax burden, streamline expenses, and dedicate more resources to development.

Depreciation policy is another important legal mechanism for tax optimization. It allows companies to account for the wear and tear of equipment and facilities, thereby reducing the taxable base. Under the IRC, mining companies can use the modified accelerated cost recovery system (MACRS), which enables assets to be depreciated faster than under the straight-line method. This is particularly important for mining projects, where capital costs are high, and assets depreciate quickly. For example, drilling and extraction equipment can be depreciated over shorter periods, enabling companies to reduce taxable income faster and free up funds for further project development.

Environmental costs associated with measures for environmental protection, land restoration, and emission reductions can, in most countries, be included as expenses, reducing the taxable base. These measures provide significant opportunities for mining companies that are required to meet environmental standards and often incur high costs for implementing environmentally safe technologies [5]. Companies may receive additional tax incentives or exemptions for implementing environmental programs. For example, by constructing treatment facilities, installing emission reduction filters, and rehabilitating land post-extraction, a company can lower its taxable base by the amount spent on fulfilling these obligations.

In addition to environmental costs, legislation allows the inclusion of other expenses related to **social projects, infrastructure improvements, and sustain-**

able development in mining regions. This includes investments in programs supporting local populations, improving social conditions, and developing local communities. Including these expenses as deductions not only helps companies reduce their tax burden but also improves their reputation and mitigates social risks.

The effective use of legal mechanisms for tax optimization requires companies to adhere to strict conditions established under national legislation. Failure to comply with rules or requirements can lead to the loss of preferential tax regimes and result in additional tax obligations and penalties. Thus, while tax incentives help reduce the tax burden, they also require strict compliance with legal norms.

Tax optimization strategies

In the context of a complex tax system, mining companies aim to utilize various tax optimization strategies designed to reduce the tax burden and improve overall efficiency. **Transfer pricing** is a method of determining the pricing of goods, services, and intangible assets in transactions between branches and subsidiaries located in different jurisdictions. For mining companies operating in both the USA and other countries, transfer pricing becomes an essential tool for tax planning, enabling the allocation of profits to minimize tax liabilities. Transfer pricing is regulated by the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), which requires intra-group transactions to adhere to the arm's length principle. This means that companies must set prices for their goods and services as if the transactions were conducted with an independent party. Transfer pricing is particularly relevant in the MI for transactions related to the export of minerals and the supply of specialized equipment. For example, a parent company can sell extracted raw materials to its overseas subsidiary at a price based on market conditions. If the subsidiary is located in a country with lower tax rates, profits can be allocated in a way that reduces the taxable income in the USA while increasing it in the low-tax jurisdiction. This allows the company to lower its overall tax burden while maintaining compliance with IRS requirements and international standards.

Another effective way to reduce the tax burden for mining companies is to develop a **tax strategy based on diversification of activities and profit allocation across different jurisdictions.** Under this strategy, a company can allocate profits to maximize their share in countries or states with lower tax rates, while leaving activities that generate less profit in high-tax regions. Mining companies may establish subsidiaries or branches in states with lower corporate tax rates or jurisdictions offering tax incentives for capital-intensive industries. Additionally, profits earned abroad may be taxed at lower rates due to international double taxation agreements. As a result, part of the income can be transferred to foreign branches located in countries with preferential tax regimes. The effective allocation of income and expenses across various jurisdictions enables mining companies to reduce their taxable base while retaining eligibility for tax incentives and benefits in high-tax countries. Such a strategy requires a thorough analysis of tax rates and legislation in different countries, as well as the development of a sustainable structure for profit allocation and activity diversification.

To successfully optimize taxation, mining companies often use **multi-tier corporate structures.** These structures allow for flexible capital management, the utilization of preferential tax rates, and the minimization of taxation at every level. A common approach involves establishing subsidiaries through which contracts for the purchase of equipment, maintenance, consulting, and legal services are executed. These subsidiaries can be registered in states with lower tax rates, enabling the mining company to reduce its taxable base [6]. Additionally, subsidiaries can enter into supply agreements with other branches and divisions of the corporation, creating an internal supply chain that optimizes tax obligations.

Contractual structures also play an important role in tax planning for international projects. For example, a company can contract exploration or other specialized services through a subsidiary registered in a jurisdiction with a more favorable tax regime. This allows a portion of the revenue to be shifted to foreign divisions with lower tax rates while ensuring compliance with legal requirements and international reporting standards.

The use of these strategies enables mining companies to effectively reduce their tax burden and maintain flexibility in managing international projects. These strategies require strict compliance with tax legislation and careful analysis of legal requirements to minimize risks and avoid potential penalties or adjustments by the IRS.

Many companies successfully implement these tax optimization strategies, demonstrating their effectiveness in practice. For example, **Newmont Corporation** actively uses depreciation deductions under the tax system to reduce its taxable base. The company has leveraged accelerated depreciation of assets under the MACRS. This has allowed them to write off a significant portion of their long-term asset costs in the early years of operation when capital investments in mining and equipment are especially high [7].

Peabody Energy is known for utilizing tax benefits related to environmental expenses, including land reclamation and carbon emission management. These expenses, included in the company's financial statements, have enabled them to reduce their taxable base by accounting for costs associated with environmental impact. Deductions for such environmental expenditures have allowed the company to offset part of its tax obligations, which has been especially important given the tightening regulations on carbon emissions [8]. These examples highlight that thoughtful application of tax strategies enables mining companies not only to adapt successfully to changes in tax and environmental regulations but also to maintain sustainable financial efficiency.

Conclusion

Mining companies face unique challenges related to high tax burdens, complex regulations, and transparency requirements. These factors necessitate a comprehensive approach to tax planning focused on compliance with legal norms and minimizing financial risks. Companies in this sector actively use various tax opti-

mization mechanisms, including depreciation deductions, international tax agreements, and accounting for environmental costs, which allow them to efficiently distribute the tax burden and maintain financial stability.

Analyzing the practices of leading companies reveals that successful tax optimization requires deep legal expertise, regular review of strategies in light of evolving legislation, and strict compliance with regulatory requirements. Thoughtful and well-implemented approaches help companies not only reduce their taxable base but also allocate freed-up resources for development and support. Thus, strategic tax planning remains one of the important factors of the competitiveness of mining companies, especially in the context of globalization and increased environmental responsibility. The use of legal tools and tax incentives within the framework of legislation enables these companies to successfully adapt to domestic and international requirements, enhancing operational efficiency and achieving long-term financial goals.

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